

Research article

Acoustic study of urban bat diversity in Veliko Tarnovo, Bulgaria

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Abstract: Urbanisation presents both challenges and opportunities for bat populations. Understanding the composition and distribution of urban bat species is the first step toward their effective conservation. However, comprehensive studies on urban bat diversity remain scarce in Bulgaria. To address this gap, we conducted a year-long acoustic survey on five different habitats in the urbanised territory of Veliko Tarnovo. Our study identified the presence of eight bat species and other distinct acoustic groups within the urban environment. Bats were found to utilise various habitats across the urban landscape. Although the activity was highest during May and September, bats remained active all year round, including the winter. Our study provides insights into synanthropic bats' seasonal and microhabitat-dependent use of urban areas. These findings will establish a baseline for future research focusing on habitat preferences, population dynamics, and interactions with urbanisation. Such research is essential for the effective management and conservation of bat populations in urban environments.

Keywords: bats, Chiroptera, echolocation, urbanisation, Veliko Tarnovo, winter bat activity

Introduction

Urbanisation is a major driver of biodiversity loss, yet our understanding of the processes shaping urban biotic communities remains limited (Czech et al., 2000; McKinney, 2006). The expansion of cities is further linked to increased pollution, water scarcity and climate change (Vitousek et al., 1997; Grimm et al., 2008). Various species exhibit different levels of susceptibility to urban environments, with some adapting to the new abundant food sources and even actively seeking proximity to human settlements, thus becoming synanthropic (Jardine, 2022). However, inhabiting the urban environment poses many risks, and it's unknown how those species will be affected in the long term (Rodewald & Gehrt, 2014). Bats (Chiroptera) are sensitive to environmental changes while also possessing traits that allow them to effectively utilise the urban environments for roosting and foraging

(Rydell, 1992; Rydell & Racey, 1995; Simon et al., 2004; Jones et al., 2009; Wolf et al., 2022). Understanding the composition and distribution of urban bat species is the first step toward their effective conservation, the prevention of potential conflicts, and the facilitation of further research.

Information about bat diversity in urban areas in Bulgaria is scarce and covers only a few of the largest cities in the country – Sofia (Tzankov et al., 2015), Plovdiv (Stoycheva et al., 2008; Tilova et al., 2008; Stoycheva et al., 2009; Deleva & Pavlova, 2022), Stara Zagora (Stoycheva et al., 2008; Stoycheva et al., 2009) and Burgas (Pandurski, 2004). The most comprehensive survey on urban bat diversity was performed by Stoycheva et al. (2008, 2009) in Plovdiv and Stara Zagora. The data on urban bats also include occasional observations (Benda et al., 2003; Tzankov et al., 2015), reports of injured bats (Deleva & Pavlova, 2022), and short-term audio recordings

(Pandurski, 2004; Deleva & Pavlova, 2022). A large hibernaculum of noctule bats (*Nyctalus noctula*) was discovered during repair works on a bridge in Plovdiv (Tilova et al., 2008). This finding suggests the presence of potentially significant, yet largely undocumented, bat populations within cities. The current threats of roost destruction and direct killing of bats during building renovation projects (Dnevnik, 2017; Deleva & Pavlova, 2022) highlight the need for long-term systematic research on urban bat diversity, which would be used for conservation purposes.

The town of Veliko Tarnovo presents a unique combination of urban areas and natural environments, including rocks, caves, riverside areas and forests. As of this research, no studies have been conducted on bat diversity in Veliko Tarnovo. The nearest data on bat diversity close to the city come from reports from the protected areas – Tarnovski Visochini, Reka Yantra, and caves near Belyakovets Village, located two kilometres northwest of Veliko Tarnovo (Benda et al., 2003, MOEW, 2024). Only one species, *Hypsugo savii* (Bonaparte, 1837), has been reported from the city centre (Benda et al., 2003). Little is known about the importance of the urban and suburban green areas for the bat diversity and the role of the Yantra river during the migration period. This study aims to evaluate bat species' diversity and seasonal activity in Veliko Tarnovo's urban environments, examining their distribution and numbers across different habitats.

Materials and methods

Study sites

The research was conducted in Veliko Tarnovo (43.07775 N, 25.61687 E), the Republic of Bulgaria (Fig. 1A). This city covers an area of 30.38 km² and is located in the central northern part of the country (Fig. 1B). Its moderately continental climate features hot summers, cold winters, and an average annual temperature of 12°C (Fick & Hijmans, 2017). Veliko Tarnovo is traversed by the Yantra River, creating meanders that cross the hills of Sveta Gora, Tsarevets, Trapezitsa and Momina Fortress, resulting in a mixture of plain and hilly terrain. The city has 13 parks and two green spaces in residential areas (Veliko Tarnovo Municipality, 2020). Approximately 50 caves and rock niches, formed in Jurassic and Cretaceous limestone, are located close to the city (BFSp,

2020). The surrounding deciduous forests, primarily composed of beech, oak, hornbeam, poplar and linden, include valuable old-growth oak and beech forests, leading to the establishment of two protected areas part of the Natura 2000 network under the Habitats Directive – “BG0000213 Tarnovski Visochini” and “BG0000610 Reka Yantra”, (Fig. 1, MOEW, 2024).

We selected five study sites that differed in urbanisation gradient and the presence of natural resources (Fig. 1). The first recording location was a residence area with multifamily units and the most urbanised study site (Fig. 1.1). The second site was an open field located on the city's outskirts, in the “BG0000213 Tarnovski Visochini” protected area (Fig. 1.2). The third site was located in a deciduous forest near a path in the “BG0000213 Tarnovski Visochini” protected area (Fig. 1.3). The fourth location was Tsarevets Fortress – a tourist destination on a hill with restored ruins, old stone walls and a church (Fig. 1.4). The fifth study site was located on the Yantra riverbank with broadleaf treelines on both sides and close to residence areas, part of the “BG0000610 Reka Yantra” protected area (Fig. 1.5).

Field research

Our study took place between December 2022 and November 2023. We used passive ultrasonic acoustic recorders AudioMoth (Hill et al., 2019) equipped with 64 GB microSD cards to monitor bat presence and activity in the selected study sites. The AudioMoth devices were mounted about two metres above ground, except in the residential area, where they were placed approximately ten metres high on a balcony. We deployed the devices for two consecutive nights in the first and the second half of each month for a total of four nights of recording per month per study site. An exception was made in December 2022 due to harsh weather. Recordings were conducted for a total of 240 nights. The devices were configured to record from 30 minutes before sunset to 30 minutes after sunrise. The sampling rate was set to 256 kHz with medium gain, no sleep interval, and a 300-second recording duration, following the instructions provided by the bat monitoring protocol in foraging sites through passive acoustic surveys of the Natural Sciences Museum of Granollers (Torre et al., 2021). Raw data is presented in [Supplementary material 01](#) .

Fig. 1. Study sites and habitats. A – Map of Veliko Tarnovo with the locations of the study sites, protected areas and land cover; B – The location of Veliko Tarnovo in Bulgaria. The different habitats are presented as follows: 1 – Residential area; 2 – Open field; 3 – Broadleaf forest; 4 – Tsarevets Fortress; 5 – Yantra riverbank.

Analysis

We utilised Kaleidoscope Pro version 5.6.4 software (Wildlife Acoustics, Inc., Maynard, USA) for sound analysis. After processing, the files were trimmed to 5-second call sequences, and noise sounds were removed. We saved the recordings in '.wav' format. After noise filtering, we obtained a total of 211770 files. For automatic identification, we selected the “Bats of Europe” settings for Bulgaria with the ‘sensitive’ option enabled. All files were further identified manually using the search phase of the calls. We applied the

following Kaleidoscope settings: FFT size 1024, window size 512 and cache size 256 MB. We first examined the shape of the calls and then collected the following parameters from several calls in each call sequence: start frequency, end frequency, frequency of maximum energy, call duration, and inter-pulse interval. We consulted with an acoustic guide (Russ, 2021). The identifications were either confirmed to a species level or grouped into species with similar echolocation characteristics. Some recordings could not be specifically identified (NoID) and were reported separately as evidence of general bat activity.

Representative bat calls were archived in the Chi-roVox acoustic database (Görföl et al., 2022). These calls were deposited as of 17.06.2024 and are available for free download [[link](#)]. Data were visualised in R version 4.1.3 (R Core Team, 2023) using the following packages: ‘ggplot2’, ‘reshape2’ and ‘ggsankey’ (Wickham, 2007, 2016; Sjöberg, 2021). The maps were created in QGIS 3.36.2 (QGIS Development Team, 2024).

Results

We observed eight bat species: *Eptesicus serotinus* (Schreber, 1774), *Pipistrellus pipistrellus* (Schreber, 1774), *Pipistrellus pygmaeus* (Leach, 1825), *Nyctalus noctula* (Schreber, 1774), *Nyctalus leisleri* (Kuhl, 1817), *Nyctalus lasiopterus* (Schreber, 1774), *Hypsugo savii* and *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum* (Schreber, 1774). In addition, we identified bats from the genera *Pipistrellus*, *Nyctalus*, *Rhinolophus*, *Myotis* and *Plecotus*. The acoustic groups that we could not identify to a species level were “*Eptesicus serotinus* or *Nyctalus leisleri* or *N. noctula* or *Vespertilio murinus*”, “*Miniopterus schreibersii* or *Pipistrellus pygmaeus*”, “*Nyctalus lasiopterus* or *Tadarida teniotis*” and “*Pipistrellus kuhlii* or *P. nathusii*”. The most frequently recorded species was *Pipistrellus pipistrellus* (89 272 detections), followed by the *P. kuhlii/nathusii* acoustic group (69 633 detections) and *Nyctalus noctula* (14 749 detections). The *Nyctalus lasiopterus/Tadarida teniotis* acoustic group had the lowest detection rate, with only eight recordings. Almost all of the recorded species and groups were present in most of the study sites, except *Pipistrellus pygmaeus* which was confidently identified only from the broadleaf forest. The *Nyctalus lasiopterus/Tadarida teniotis* acoustic group was recorded in the residential area, Tsarevets Fortress and Yantra riverbank. The *Rhinolophus* sp. group was detected in the less urbanised study sites – open field, broadleaf forest and Tsarevets Fortress. The total percentages of bats identified to species level were 50.17%, allocated to acoustic groups – 43.27%, and unidentified – 6.56%. The proportion of recordings for the identified species and acoustic groups, along with their availability in the study sites, are shown in Fig. 2.

Bats were active throughout all of the study months across all locations (Fig. 3). The highest activity was recorded at the Yantra riverbank, peaking in

September and May 2023. The difference in activity levels in this study site was more than 80-fold, with the lowest activity recorded in December 2022. In the Residence area, activity peaked in July, August and September. Both of those locations also exhibit the highest winter activity. At Tsarevets Fortress, bat activity peaked in May, followed by June, September and March. Similar peaks were recorded in the open field site. This location, along with the Broadleaf forest showed relatively constant and lower activity compared to the other three locations. The difference in peak activity between the sites was more than 14-fold.

Discussion

Our study revealed the presence of eight bat species and identified eight distinct acoustic groups within the urban environment of Veliko Tarnovo. Species richness was relatively homogenous across the study sites. The most frequently identified species were *Pipistrellus pipistrellus*, *P. kuhlii/nathusii* (acoustic group) and *Nyctalus noctula*. Those species are commonly found in urban areas in Europe (Dietz & Kiefer, 2015; Russ, 2021; Russo, 2023; Teixeira & Russo, 2021) and Bulgaria (Pandurski, 2004; Stoycheva et al., 2009; Tzankov et al., 2015; Deleva & Pavlova, 2022). Even though we could not differentiate between *Pipistrellus kuhlii* and *P. nathusii* due to their overlapping echolocation calls (Russ, 2021; Teixeira & Russo, 2021), it is likely that both species were present in the area. Other less recorded species – *Plecotus austriacus*, *Eptesicus serotinus*, *Vespertilio murinus* and *Hypsugo savii* could also be observed in urban environments (Kipson et al., 2023; Martinoli et al., 2023; Razgour, 2023; Safi, 2023; Russo, 2023). This is the case with other similar studies made in the country (Stoycheva et al., 2009; Tzankov et al., 2015; Deleva & Pavlova, 2022). We have identified *Nyctalus lasiopterus* at every study site. This species is rarely reported due to its high-altitude aerial hawking (Dietz & Kiefer, 2015; Estók et al., 2021). By considering the acoustic diagnostic characteristics and overlaps of each species (Dietz & Kiefer, 2015; Russ, 2021; Russo, 2023), we identified *N. lasiopterus* in a total of 212 recordings.

The Yantra river and riparian habitats near the city could provide suitable environments for bat species that rely on their availability, such as *Eptesicus serotinus*, *Hypsugo savii*, *Nyctalus leisleri*, *Pipi-*

Fig. 2. Sankey graph representing the proportion of records per species and acoustic groups (left side of the graph) in the study sites. Species and acoustic group abbreviations as follows: Eptser – *Eptesicus serotinus*; Hypsav – *Hypsugo savii*; Nyclas – *Nyctalus lasiopterus*; Nyclei – *N. leisleri*; Nycnoc – *N. noctula*; Pippip – *Pipistrellus pipistrellus*; Ppyg – *P. pygmaeus*; Rhifer – *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*; EptNycVes – *E. serotinus*, *N. noctula*, *N. leisleri*, *Vespertilio murinus*; MyoSp – *Myotis* sp.; PpygMin – *P. pygmaeus*, *Miniopterus schreibersii*; NycSp – *N. noctula*, *N. leisleri*; TadNyc – *Tadarida teniotis*, *N. lasiopterus*; Pkuhnat – *P. kuhlii*, *P. nathusii*; PleSp – *Plecotus auritus*, *Pl. austriacus*; Rhipmeheur – *Rh. hipposideros*, *Rh. mehelyi*. *Rh. euryale*; NoID – unidentified, general bat activity.

stellus pygmaeus, *Tadarida teniotis* and *Vespertilio murinus* (Catto et al., 1996; Marques et al., 2004; Dietz & Kiefer, 2015; Georgiakakis et al., 2021; Russ, 2021; Russ & Teixeira, 2021; Rydell & Boonman,

2021). The presence of broadleaf forests surrounding the urban matrix could explain the recordings of species such as *Miniopterus schreibersii*, *Myotis myotis*, *Nyctalus lasiopterus*, *Plecotus auritus*, *Rhino-*

Fig. 3. Heatmap presenting the total monthly bat acoustic activity per location. The first number in each cell presents the activity level while the number in the brackets presents the number of species and acoustic groups recorded during the month.

lophus euryale and *Rh. hipposideros* (Audet, 1990; Entwistle et al., 1996; Rudolph et al., 2009; Murphy et al., 2012; Dietz & Kiefer, 2015; Andrews et al., 2021; Estók et al., 2021; Papadatou et al., 2021; Russ, 2021). It is also not unlikely that some recorded cave-dwelling species, such as *Myotis blythii*, *M. myotis*, *Rhinolophus euryale*, *Rh. ferrumequinum*, *Rh. hipposideros* and *Rh. mehelyi* (Ransome, 1971; Rodrigues et al., 2003; Schofield & McAney, 2008; Dietz & Kiefer, 2015; Mucedda & Pidinchedda, 2021; Papadatou et al., 2021; Ransome, 2023), also pass through Veliko Tarnovo in their flight path to and from their roosts located close to the city.

We observed varying levels of bat activity at the selected sites, even though the longest distance between them was only 2.25 km. This indicates that local factors in urban environments significantly influence bat behaviour and habitat use, even within a small study area. During the month with the highest overall activity, some sites exhibited 13 times more bat activity than others. The highest bat activity was recorded

at the Yantra riverbank, supporting the crucial role urban rivers play for bats, as detailed in recent studies (Kohyt et al., 2024). The detector at the Yantra riverbank was specifically deployed next to calm open water, where the surface provides an important foraging area for bats. There were two pronounced activity peaks at this location in May and September, coinciding with the migration period, which supports the potential importance of Yantra River in providing food and water availability during this time. Additionally, rivers are considered important linear landscape features for bats during migration (Furmankiewicz & Kucharska, 2009), further suggesting the potential role of this river. However, more data and different experimental setups are needed to investigate this. Conversely, recent acoustic and radiotelemetry studies in the United States found no evidence that bats specifically follow rivers during migration (Krauel et al., 2017; Cortes & Gillam, 2020).

The Residence area was also characterised by higher bat activity, which could be attributed to both

the availability of streetlights, which are linked to increased insect abundance, and the availability of roosting opportunities. At this study site, recordings were taken from a balcony at a height of 10 m. The variation in detector deployment height could partly explain the differences in activity levels (Collins & Jones, 2009). In their study, the detectors placed at a height of 30 m showed a reduction in the number of *Pipistrellus* passes, a trend not observed in our survey. In fact, the number of passes from this genus was nearly as high as those recorded at the river location. However, we observed a reduction in the activity of other predominant bat species and acoustic groups, such as *Nyctalus noctula* and *Myotis*, known to be constrained and to avoid artificial lights (Stone et al., 2012; Voigt et al., 2020). The abundance of streetlights in the study location likely contributed to this reduction. Moreover, the potential cumulative and long-term effect of artificial lighting on bats is still unknown (Stone et al., 2015). The overall high acoustic activity around streetlights should be interpreted with caution due to the shift in insect distribution, known as the “vacuum effect,” which alters resource availability (Russo et al., 2019). Furthermore, it is known to cause niche segregation in bats and to increase the risk of predation (Rowse et al., 2015; Salinas-Ramos et al., 2021).

The total activity levels in the Tsarevets Fortress were average, with a peak in activity during May. Positioned in the hilly part of the town, this site provides numerous bat roosting opportunities in the rock cracks, niches, ruins and fortress walls. Recordings of *Nyctalus* species and *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum* were the most abundant at this site. Further analyses of the timing of activity could shed more light on bats’ use and the importance of this location. Unsurprisingly, the Broadleaf forest exhibited the least activity, likely due to the increased vegetation density, which is known to reduce bat activity (Obrist et al., 2011). However, this was the only location where we recorded *Pipistrellus pygmaeus* and the highest activity of the acoustic group of *Rhinolophus* sp. Interestingly the Open field site showed the second lowest activity levels. In this location, we recorded the highest activity of the *Plecotus* group. Our results should not undermine the importance of these habitats for bats, especially those less adapted to urbanisation and with more specialised diets. These habitats offer essential resources and roosting options with fewer risk factors compared to more urbanised areas.

Bats were active throughout the 12-month recording period, with the highest activity observed between May and September 2023, and the lowest in December 2022 and January 2023. Winter bat activity in urban areas has been previously reported (Krauel & LeBuhn, 2016; Barros et al., 2017). In our study, the highest winter bat activity was recorded in the residential area and the river, which further supports the importance of those habitats during the winter (Mas et al., 2022). Insect biomass and diversity are reduced during the winter months (Williams, 1961), but a special complex of invertebrates remains and supports bats during their arousal from hibernation (Taylor, 1963; Toshkova et al., 2023). Thus, urbanised habitats with artificial lights that attract insects could provide valuable foraging habitats for bats that do not exhibit light avoidance behaviour. However, this is not typical for most bat species (Voigt et al., 2018). This further raises concerns about generating resource imbalances during periods of scarcity, a topic that needs research attention.

To our knowledge, this is the longest and most consistent urban acoustic monitoring of bats in Bulgaria and the first to survey the activity during the entire night. This approach will allow for future in-depth exploration of the spatial and temporal activity differences and how bats utilise the selected habitats. Studies have indicated that human evening activities can adversely affect bat activity in urban areas (Li et al., 2020), and further investigation into the effect of the time of the working week on recording activity can complement our work. Given the general limitations of acoustic surveys, which can make species identification challenging or impossible, future efforts in roost surveys and mist netting are essential. These efforts could support our current findings and potentially reveal a greater diversity of bats, contributing to urban bat conservation strategies and management.

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Authors' contribution

(using [CrediT](#))

Maksim Kolev: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, methodology, project administration, resources, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Ilya Acosta-Pankov: conceptualisation, methodology, resources, supervision, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Nia Toshkova: formal analysis, funding acquisition, resources, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Stanimira Deleva: conceptualisation, supervision, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing.

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Supplementary materials

01

Document title: The supplementary material represents merged tables from the Kaleidoscope pro software 5.6.4 after analysis of the recordings from all 240 nights of recording with information on dates, times of recording, locations, echolocation call characteristics, automatic and manual call identifications

Kind of document: Microsoft Excel (OpenXML)

MIME type: application/vnd.openxmlformats-officedocument.spreadsheetml.sheet

Document name: 000566000462024-01.xlsx

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02

Document title: The table represents information on the 111 recordings uploaded to the ChiroVox bat sound library, which can be found on the following link: https://www.chirovox.org/contributor_map.php?q=%D0%9Caksim%20Kolev

https://www.chirovox.org/contributor_map.php?q=%D0%9Caksim%20Kolev

Kind of document: Microsoft Excel (OpenXML)

MIME type: application/vnd.openxmlformats-officedocument.spreadsheetml.sheet

Document name: 000566000462024-02.xlsx

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A dataset, containing raw data on recording locations, dates, times, echolocation call characteristics, automatic and manual call identifications to species or acoustic groups, and a table with information on the sound files uploaded to the ChiroVox bat sound library are available online: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.25942819>